

InChildHealth

We are researching the impact of indoor air quality on childrens' health.

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WHAT ARE WE INVESTIGATING AND WHY

Indoor air quality is an important factor in health and well-being, as we often spend more than 90% of our time indoors.

Children spend much of this time in **schools** and at home, where they are exposed to different physical, chemical and biological conditions.

Numerous scientific studies indicate that **indoor air quality in schools** can affect childrens' health and academic success. But there is a lack of detailed knowledge about the factors of good indoor air quality and a better understanding of possible sources of pollutants. The Covid-19 pandemic has also shown how important it is to better understand the quality of indoor air quality in schools and to find out how it affects the spread of respiratory diseases, for example.

That's why INCHILDHEALTH is researching indoor air quality factors and their impact on the health of school children aged 6-13 years. Environments in which the children spend most of their time are examined.

RESEARCH PROJECT

To this end, 15 European research institutions from the natural and social sciences are working together.

CITIZEN SCIENCE

But without the cooperation with the schools, the study would not work. Therefore, school children are invited to be actively involved in the research activities.

WHO WE ARE

INCHILDHEALTH is a European research project with 15 partners from natural and social sciences. The project is coordinated by the Aalto University in Finland.

Funded by the European Union

WHEN & WHERE WILL THE STUDY BE CONDUCTED

INCHILDHEALTH examines the indoor air quality of schools in **7 European cities**.

Activities will be carried out in the school years 2023/24 and 2024/25.

HOW THE STUDY WILL BE CONDUCTED

1. Measurement of air quality

Our research work aims to measure indoor air quality and identify the causes of indoor pollutant emissions. For this purpose, measuring devices are placed in selected classrooms in such a way that they do not interfere with the school process and do not endanger the safety of school attendance. The devices measure the following factors:

- physical factors (e.g. particulates, temperature and relative humidity)
- chemical factors (e.g. gaseous compounds such as VOC, CO₂, CO, NO₂)
- biological factors (e.g. bacteria, viruses, fungi)

For the investigation, possible sources of pollutants and air hygiene options in the affected rooms are also recorded (e.g. number of windows, used building materials, furniture material, used cleaning material). In addition, pollutants in the outside air, noise and external environmental influences, such as the location of the school on important traffic routes, are documented.

2. Testing of interventions

In controlled intervention we are testing studies cost- and user-friendly solutions to improve the indoor air quality in schools in 7 European cities. Researchers examine the effectiveness of various measures to improve indoor air quality, such as ventilation systems, natural ventilation, plants, different cleaning products, etc.

3. Epidemiological study

A health study is also being carried out in the 3 cities Helsinki, Copenhagen and Barcelona, which examines the influence of indoor air quality on the health and well-being of school children. Information on the well-being and possible illnesses of the children is collected at regular intervals.

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF PARTICIPATION

3-5 schools in each city can take part in the InChildHealth citizen science activities. From these citizen science activities the following advantages arise.

- ◆ Schools can actively integrate the research work into their courses. Accompanied by researchers, students carry out research activities themselves - we call this „Citizen Science“. Supporting presentations and teaching materials are provided by the project partners in consultation with the teachers.
- ◆ By taking part, students learn why good air quality is important, how it can be influenced and how they can do something for their health. They will learn how researchers work and which principles are followed in research.
- ◆ The parents of the pupils also receive information on indoor air quality.
- ◆ Schools receive current data on the indoor air conditions of the selected classrooms.
- ◆ School representatives will be invited to the final presentation of the project, where the results of the study will be presented and discussed.
- ◆ The research results are fed back into measures that improve the indoor air quality in schools and increase the well-being of the children.

CONSENT

*School children can ONLY take part in the study as citizen scientists if their legal guardians sign a **declaration of consent**. This is prepared by the research partners together with the information material for the parents.*

WHAT ARE PARTICIPATION OPPORTUNITIES FOR SCHOOLS

Depending on the interests, needs and curricula of the schools, there are several ways to actively participate in the InChildHealth project. In addition to passive participation by only setting up the measuring devices, there are other options for contributing to the project.

Schools can choose from the following modules depending on their interests:

Citizen Science Module 1: “Air Quality Checker”

In this module, students learn why indoor air quality is so important and how they can positively influence it. Through small joint activities, they gain practical insights into the working methods of researchers.

The module includes the following activities, which are discussed in detail with the school and the responsible teachers:

Mini-Workshop:

- ◆ Researchers give a presentation introducing school children to various factors affecting indoor air quality and how children can take active steps to improve the air they breathe.
- ◆ The presentation is complemented by small practical activities carried out by the school children.
- ◆ The duration of this mini-workshop is about two teaching units and is supported by teaching material that is prepared in advance in coordination with the responsible teacher.

Walkthrough (optional):

- ◆ The school children support the researcher’s work in describing the school building and the classrooms. Using a template, they describe those aspects that influence indoor air quality, such as wall, floor and furniture materials, classroom size, number of windows, etc.
- ◆ The collected data will be used by the researchers in their study.
- ◆ The duration is approx. one teaching unit and is determined in advance in coordination with the teacher.

WHAT ARE PARTICIPATION OPPORTUNITIES FOR SCHOOLS

Citizen Science Module 2: “Air Quality Researcher”

In this module, school children explore the air particles in their classroom. They learn what it means to define a research question, collect data on bacteria and fungi, evaluate them and work together to develop measures that can help to improve the indoor air quality in their classroom.

The module includes the following activities, which are discussed in detail with the school and the responsible teachers:

In addition to the mini-workshop and the optional walkthrough of module 1, the school children become researcher as part of the:

Bioaerosol Learning Days:

- ◆ The school children learn to distinguish between biological particles in the air, such as bacteria, viruses and fungi, and understand their impact on their health.
- ◆ They collect particle samples, analyze them and use the data they collect to develop measures to improve air quality. The collected data from the school children will be used by the researchers in their study.
- ◆ The researchers support the whole process, by preparing the equipment, carrying out the activities together with the school children and providing the teachers with additional teaching materials.
- ◆ The activities last about 6-8 teaching units and can be adapted to the timetable. The detailed time planning is discussed individually with the responsible persons in the preparatory phase.
- ◆ Specific activities related to sampling and analysis can also be customized.

WHAT ARE PARTICIPATION OPPORTUNITIES FOR SCHOOLS

Citizen Science Module 3: “Air Quality PI”

In this module, the school children conduct their own research study. With the help of the researchers, they are developing an experiment that investigates the connection between air quality and health. To do this, they (experimentally) change the air quality, e.g. by installing an air filter, and then measuring whether a certain health parameter changes.

The module includes the following activities, which are discussed in detail with the school and the responsible teachers:

In addition to the mini-workshop and optional walkthrough of module 1, the school children develop their own study as part of the:

Air Quality Research Days:

- After an introduction to the essential factors of good indoor air quality, the school children develop their own research study:
 - What research question do they want to investigate?
 - Which air quality data should be measured?
 - How should it be measured?
 - How should the data be analyzed?
- All these phases are supported by the scientists.
- ◆ These activities are expected to last 8-10 teaching units and can be spread over several days depending on the curriculum. They are planned in advance together with the responsible teachers and supported by scientists with teaching materials, measuring devices and tools for data analysis.
- ◆ Specific activities related to sampling and analysis can also be customized.

DATA AND RESULTS OF THE STUDY

What are the results of the study for?

The study results deepen the knowledge about the factors of good indoor air quality as well as possible sources of pollutants and their effects on the well-being of children. They are intended to contribute to the promotion of public guidelines and measures, such as ventilation recommendations in schools.

The results of the study will be published in scientific journals and are freely accessible. The participating school children are not identifiable at any time. Upon request, the schools will be informed about the publication of the articles.

YOU ARE INTERESTED, YOU HAVE QUESTIONS?

If you are interested in [participating in the InChildHealth project](#), please get in touch:

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More information about the project will be available here in the future:

www.inchildhealth.eu

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